

ASSESSMENT OF THE ATTITUDES OF SENIOR STUDENTS IN FRENCH TEACHING PROGRAMME WITH REGARDS TO USE OF TECHNOLOGY & CHALLENGES CONFRONTED

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Abstract

The objective of this research is to exert the attitudes of senior students (pre-service teachers) in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology, as well as identifying the frequently used technological tools & materials, including the challenges confronted while using these tools & materials. The research was carried out on 30 teacher candidates, studying in French Teaching Programme within the Department of Foreign Languages Education, in Anadolu University - Faculty of Education. Categorized as a qualitative & quantitative study, the research was carried out using the one-sample final-test research model. The quantitative data of the research was obtained using the Technological Attitude Scale, thus performing statistical analyses. On the other hand, the qualitative data was collected with 2 open-ended questions addressed to the students. Assessment of the answers given for these questions was obtained using the document analysis method, while performing frequency & percentage analysis. Considering the findings obtained from the research, it can be said that the senior students in French Teaching Programme were familiar with the technological tools & materials, and that they developed positive attitudes with regards to the use of these tools & materials. It was observed that the main tools & materials that are frequently used in class were computers, smart boards, and correspondingly the Office programs. It was ascertained that almost half of the students did not confront any problem with regards to the use of technological tools & materials. The main challenges confronted by the students are the retardation of technological tools, internet connection cut-off, including not having the required knowledge on certain programs.

Keywords: attitude, foreign language teaching and learning, using technology, senior students

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1. Introduction

In today's world, technology has become one of the most essential parts of our Daily lives. The utilization area of technological tools and materials have expanded so much that there is almost no environment, where it is not used. Therefore, one of the most significant areas, where technology is utilized, is the education and training area. Technology is described under various definitions. According to Simon (1983, quoted by Alpar et. al., 2007:22), *"technology is a discipline designed by the human kind for superiority over nature by utilization of science"*. As to McDermott (1981, quoted by Alpar et. al., 2007:22) *"Technology, in its concrete, empirical meaning, refers fundamentally to systems of rationalized control over large groups of men, events and machines by small groups of technically skilled men operating through an organized hierarchy"*. Briefly, technology, in the simplest form, can be described as *"the tools and materials developed by people to have control over and change its physical environment"* (TDK – Turkish Language Association).

With the technological advancements being integrated into education & training environments, the terms "educational technology" and "instructional technology" have been brought forward. Some researchers use these two terms under an interchangeable manner.

"To some, the term "instructional technologies" means any kind of tools, devices and materials used for supporting in-class learning activities and facilitating the learning process, while by others, it is defined as an innovative and particular approach utilized during teaching-learning processes in order for the designated aims to be achieved in education" (Adıgüzel, 2010:3). In other words, *"educational technology is the process for designing, developing, implementing and evaluating the tools, materials, methods and techniques taking the respective area into consideration, based on the scientific information"* (Ersoy: 8). Hence, one of the most critical objectives of educational technologies is the effective learning & teaching.

On the other hand, educational technology seeks the answer for the question "How do we teach?". Therefore, the educational technology is not only defined as teaching, but also as the utilization of scientific information for designing, implementing and evaluating the methodologies and processes with regards to each and every area that is within the scope of education (learning, management, evaluation, material design, etc.) (İbid.: 8). The objectives of educational technology can be defined as follows (İbid.: 9):

- *"Getting the educational services to larger masses,*
- *Making the teaching-learning processes more efficient,*
- *Individualizing the teaching-learning activities,*
- *Organizing the activities for teaching-learning process,*
- *Setting the educational requirements and capacities as scientific research object,*
- *Turning the educational institutions into practical form,*
- *Ensuring the continuation of teaching programmes,*
- *Regulating and controlling the environmental factors,*
- *Adopting the learning process to the skills of the student,*

- *Putting the solutions of problems with regards to education into practice”.*

Countries, following and using the technological innovations aims on preparing the future generations for their lives by providing them with the opportunity for high-quality education via well-equipped environments in terms of integrating these technological innovations into their educational environments. Cradler (1996) pointed out that the educational technologies can be structured suitably for educational curriculums followed in schools with such factors as students’ needs, sufficiency of resources, attitudes towards technology, including the procurement of technical support and respective guidance (Adıgüzel, 2010:2).

Roblyer and Edwards (2005, quoted by İbid., 2010:2) described the necessity for utilization of educational technologies in the process of teaching-learning by the teachers under five critical principles:

- Motivation;
- Educational skills;
- Qualification and efficiency of the teacher;
- Requirement of information age;
- Supporting the teaching methods and techniques.

1.1. History of Technology Utilization in Education

Integrating the technology into schools starts primarily with the configuration of technological equipment, a series of software, as well as the learning content in parallel with the former. It can be conferred that the use of technology in education is seen in United States of America, being in the first place, including other developed countries. Therefore, with the coming of internet in 1990s led an increase with regards to the usage of digital technologies in every part of the society, thus making the digital revolution inevitable to rise to prominence in schools in 2000s (Bétrancourt, 2011:2). *“In today’s world, where the amount of information has grown, the information is spread far and wide, thus making it easier to reach information, it is not deemed as a requirement to utilize the information technologies in education, as in a large number of other areas, particularly until the end of twentieth century”* (Kozikoğlu, 374:2013). Özden (2003, quoted by Cereci) categorizes the steps for use of technology in education as follows:

- *“Visual materials were used educational military movies in World Wars I and II.*
- *TV was started to be used for education in the beginning of 1950s, thus constituting the departments of visual-audial technologies in universities.*
- *Ford Foundation provided support for education via television between 1950-1960.*
- *In 1967, American Research Institute developed personal educational programmes named as “Need-based Learning”.*

The most frequently used technological tool in today’s environment-training environments is undoubtedly the computers. As mentioned by Özden (2003, quoted by ibid.), the steps for use of computers in education institutions can be listed as follows:

- The computers were introduced to the education institutions for the large-scale universities as oriented to administrative affairs in 1950s.

- In 1960s, the studies for the development of computer-based educational programmes were initiated. One of these projects was PLATO.
- In 1970s, more computers of schools were started to be used for administrative purposes.
- In 1972, TICCIT (Time-Shared Interactive Computer Controlled Information Television) system was started to be developed.
- A tendency from personal computers to network systems and internet appeared with the advancements in internet after 1970s.
- It became the beginning of a new era with the swift-participation of the countries in the NFSNET network backbone, into which Turkey was integrated in 1993, as well as the commencement of a new technological contest following its heavy increase.

According to the use of technology in Turkey, *"...it can be seen that the first time for the use of internet was in April-1993. The first connection was made from Middle East Technical University, and internet was extended primarily within universities in Turkey. Hence, the connections from Ege University in 1994, Bilkent and Bogazici University in 1995 and Istanbul Technical University in the early part of 1996 were made"* (Kaya, 2006: 310). Many of our universities, including a number of public institutions were provided with internet connection via Middle East Technical University between 1993 – 1996 (ibid.: 310).

Today, the importance of the use of technology in education was highlighted one more time with FATİH project (Movement for Increasing the Opportunities and Technological Advancement), extended nationally within the scope of primary and secondary education. *"Thanks to this system, the interaction between the teacher and the student will be ensured with board-tablet using the class management, while effectively using the knowledge acquisition/learning processes, providing the class-management and the teacher with the opportunity to share the in-class materials with the students, sending the homework, as well as measuring the in-class learning levels of the students under a more controlled manner"* (Fatih Project in Education).

1.2. Contributions by Technology to Education-Training

As stated in the previous studies, it is possible to ensure effective learning in class environments within each and every phase of education & training is possible only via keeping at least one of the interactions between the student-teacher, student-student, student-content and student-environment on a high level, while making use of educational technologies in order to ensure keeping one of these interactions on highly level (Kaya, 3:2006).

Successful integration of technology into education leads to certain positive contributions like improving the quality in education & training, increasing the success levels of students in schools, strengthening the motivation and determination for learning (Masrafi, 2015:29). To exemplify, the students may be presented with opportunities that are different from ordinary education-training environments, in

order to improve the motivation for learning and academic success levels, particularly in foreign language classes, by utilization of information technologies.

In our era, information technologies have contributed a lot in many areas, including the education. It can be clearly said that both the foreign language lessons and other respective courses are taught in computer environment. Accordingly, the use of computers in education & training environments does not only improve the quality of education, but also allowing it to be provided for many people simultaneously.

“Introducing the technology to schools simply as a “product” is not enough for an effective usage. What matters is that the student, teacher, family and management use the technology fit for their personal purposes, that it provides benefits for learning-teaching process, that it becomes self-sufficient, that it is integrated into the school culture, as well as leading for future innovations” (Aşkar, 1999:3).

It is highlighted in a number of studies that it is recognized as a must to integrate technology into education in order for training well-appointed individuals by making teaching-learning processes more efficient (Konur, Sezen and Tekbıyık, 2008). *“The use of technology in education contributes in various ways like simplifying the learning process, shortening the learning time, as well as saving up on the learning costs” (Akkoyunlu, 1998, quoted by Daşdemir et.al., 2012).*

Therefore, it can be said that integrating information and communication technologies into education plays a critical role in improving the quality of education & training and the success levels of students, strengthening the motivation and determination of the students.

But, it will be possible for the use of this technology in educational environments only with the teachers and students having the required knowledge qualifications on the respective area. Considering that today’s students are literally living with certain technological tools like computers, tablets, smart phones, smart-boards, etc. in classes, it seems inevitable for the undergraduate students, who are the teacher candidates of future, to be equipped with the respective knowledge required for the use of these tools & materials during their undergraduate education.

Accordingly, *“the teachers must possess the knowledge and skills on educational technologies within this period, while utilizing these technologies effectively in order to support the learning performances in school, as well” (Adıgüzel, 2010, quoted by).*

However, the teachers are required at first *“to determine the manner of contribution by the selected technologies to the lesson content and performance of teaching activities along with the knowledge and skills that are to be possessed with regards to the technologies to be used, as well as drawing up a comprehensive plan taking certain matters like environment and environmental conditions, learning differences of the students and their preferences, lesson content, etc. into consideration” (Pamuk, Ülken and Dilek 2012).*

1.3. Technological Tools-Materials Used in Education

The technological tools & materials used in education & training are not limited to solely computers, which is needless to say. The technological tools & materials used in

today's class environments can be listed as internet, interactive smart board, computer (laptop computer), overhead projector, television, video, tape recorder, projector, cassette player (for reading audio CD), CD player, USB, USB memory, blackboard. The most frequently used ones among these are doubtfully internet, interactive smart boards, projector and USB memories:

- The more the *internet* is used for educational purposes, the more it has started to be recognized as an important educational tool. The use of internet provides convenience in terms of saving on time both for the student and the teacher. Additionally, the internet eliminates the challenges with regards to distance, while allowing the students & teachers to Exchange information without the necessity to be within the same place, as well as providing the students with the opportunity to carry out personal studies. As Kaya pointed out (2006: 322), today, internet is frequently used within the following educational environments:
 - *“lecturing to students,*
 - *organizing argumentative lesson environments for students,*
 - *carrying out the duties of thesis advisor.”*

The education & training environments vary on the internet. We can summarize these groups under 4 categories: websites, text-based conference (real time interactive chat, virtual reality, delayed time chat, electronic mail, discussion lists, news groups), voice conference and video conference (ibid., 2006:323). Correspondingly, we can list the objectives for the frequent use of internet in Higher Education as follows (ibid., 238):

- *“providing distance education for people from all over the world,*
- *providing the students with the opportunities to attend the lessons, which are not introduced within a specific campus,*
- *providing the students with the opportunity to attend the lessons, which are not introduced within various universities,*
- *providing those taking distance education with the opportunity to attend to a class, while showing the application examples, without the need to navigate between the campuses,*
- *ensuring that the application processes are demonstrated to the students,*
- *ensuring the interaction between the students and the experts from around the world,*
- *Enabling the students, who wish to apply for a job, to have interviews with the respective authorities.*

The use of internet in education & training is not limited to only those stated above. A number of platforms are available, enabling all the students within the class to attend, as well as carrying out various activities, thanks to the internet. One of these platforms is Kahoot. Kahoot is a free platform, which is quite simple to put into practice and prepare. It is used for managing the exams, discussions and surveys.

As a matter of fact, it is a game-based response system, played in real time by the whole class. The registration can be made via “getkahoot.com” (<https://www.vcsu.edu/cmsfiles/433/373bd6a842.pdf>). The questions prepared by the teachers are displayed and answered with the help of a code. The application is based

on the multiple-choice questions reflected to the display, and on answering these questions by students via smart phones, tablets and computers.

Another example for this kind of application is the “Quizlet”. On this website, which can be reached via “Quizlet.com”, it is emphasized on learning words from foreign languages. The students are provided with the opportunity to study not only their personal word lists, but also the word lists of other users by creating visual and audio flashcards, as free of charge (<https://quizlet.com/89313049/what-is-quizlet-flash-cards/>).

- *Interactive smart boards* are a technological tool, which is frequently used both in primary & secondary and also in higher education. It was aimed at delivering the Information Technology (IT) Equipment, possessing the capacity to provide support for education, to all the schools, classrooms, teacher and students within the scope of Fatih Project in Education, thus providing the elementary schools with smart boards. These boards appear to us as a device equipped with a new-age smart board instead of old-school green boards in a simple structure, which do not require technical knowledge, appealing to the individuals of our ear, and which can be used by the teachers and students possessing a technological knowledge on a baseline level (<http://fatihprojesi.meb.gov.tr/etkilesimli-tahta/>).

It can be clearly seen that the Interactive Board, developed against the challenges with regards to the use of the existing smart boards (need for an external computer connection, higher costs on the lamp-change after the expiration, not receiving a healthy image under bright conditions, etc.), is a much more ideal solution for educational environments (ibid., 201).

- *USB memories* are fast to plug-in / plug-out, small and light data storage tools. They have various amounts of storage (2, 4, 16, 32 GB and 1 TB memory options are available). Fast and easy access is ensured by these devices (<http://blog.ofix.com/usb-bellekler/>). Mainly used for storing data like homework, presentation files, various videos by the students, these products are named as “flash drives”.

Experiencing the use of technology within the lessons of Higher Education institutions (use of interactive smart boards, homework presentation prepared via Power Point, delivering presentation by using an overhead projector, preparing the homework by using the MS Office programs, the opportunity to make researches on the internet, etc.) makes it a must for the students to have the required knowledge and skills with regards to this area. Students, having knowledge on the use of technological tools & materials will graduate as qualified in this area, thus having the opportunity to effortlessly utilize the technological knowledge on the institutions, in which they are employed.

However, the previous studies suggested that the self-confidence and competency of the teachers have an influence on the use of technology (Oral, 2008, quoted by Erdemir et. al., 2009:100), that the academic staff of institutions that train teachers is not recognized as the role model in terms of the use of technology, and that

the students are not required to use technology, at all (Deubel, 2003, Crowther, Keller & Waddoups, 2004, quoted by *ibid.*, 2009:100).

Therefore, it is a must for the teacher candidates, as the future teachers, to improve themselves by recognizing the role of technology in education, while having the skills to use the technological tools & materials in the education & training environments, in order not to be kept behind from technological advancements, when they are employed.

With this study, it is aimed at identifying the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme within the Department of Foreign Languages Education with regards to the use of technological tools and materials in education & training, as well as determining the challenges confronted as using these tools and materials. Within the framework of this study, the following questions were exerted to be answered:

1. What are the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education & training?
2. Do the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme in education & training differ as gender-based?
3. What are the challenges that are frequently confronted by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme as using the technology in education & training?
4. What are the technological tools & materials that are frequently preferred with regards to the use of technology in education & training by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme?

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

As a qualitative and quantitative study carried out in the academic year 2017-2018, the pattern of this study was one-sample final test research model. One-sample final-test model can be described as applying the independent variable on a randomly selected single sample, and measuring of the result on the dependent variable (Karasar, 1995:96). The research group of this study comprises of 30 senior students (teacher candidates) studying in French Teaching Programme within Anadolu University – Faculty of Education. All the students participating in the research serve their internship for 14 weeks and lecture for high school students in secondary education institution, of which second foreign language is French within the Ministry of National Education and within the scope of School Experience. The descriptive information for the participants can be seen on Table 1. As can be clearly seen, 50% of them are female ($f=15$), while 50% of them are male ($f=15$).

Table 1: Distribution of Teacher Candidates by Gender

Gender	<i>f</i>	%
Female	15	50.0
Male	15	50.0
Total	30	100.0

2.2. Data Collection

Within the scope of this research, the main objective is to identify the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technological tools and materials in education & training. The data collection for the research was performed within two phases. The quantitative data of the research was obtained by using the “Technological Attitude Scale” developed by Yavuz (2009) in order to identify the attitudes of the students. The scale comprises of 5 subheadings and 19 articles. These subheadings were categorized as follows: “the status of technological tools not being utilized in education”, “the status of technological tools being utilized in education”, “influences of technology in educational life”, “teaching the use of technological tools” and “evaluation of technological tools. There are 5 negative and 14 positive articles in this scale.

The Technological Attitude Scale (TAS) was prepared as 5 point likert, thus being organized as “Strongly agree” (5), “Agree” (4), “Neutral” (3), “Disagree” (2), “Strongly disagree” (1). The answers given by the students in the scale were coded as point-based from 5 to 1 for positive articles, and from 1 to 5 for negative articles. Hence, the lowest score for the scale is 19, while the highest one is 95.

The qualitative data of the research was obtained by the analysis of answers given by the students to the open-ended questions like “*What are the challenges that you confront while using technological tools & materials?*” and “*What are the technological tools & materials that you use for your lessons (doing homework, preparing presentation, lecturing in secondary schools, etc.), with document, frequency and percentage analyses?*”

The document analysis (document review) comprises of the analysis of written materials on the fact(s) that are aimed to be subjected to research. For a research on education, the following can be utilized: school books, programme directive, intramural and extramural correspondence, student registries, meeting reports, counselling records and files for students, handbooks of students and teachers, lessons, homework and exams of the students, lessons and unit plans, teacher files, official documents for education, etc. (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2016). In addition to those stated above, “*the personal documents and papers like the memories, diaries, private letters, confessions, including the press, periodical written resources, magazine, journals and books can be subjected to document analysis, as well*” (Bailey, 1982:302-303).

2.3. Findings and Comments

Aiming at identifying the attitudes of senior students studying in the Department of French Teaching with regards to the use of technological tools and materials in education & training, including the challenges confronted while using these tools and

materials, this study laid out the respective findings within the framework of research questions.

The descriptive statistics were used for receiving an answer to the following question as the first problem in the research “*What are the attitudes of senior students studying in the French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education & training?*” The statistics for the attitudes of students with regards to the use of technology in education & training can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for the total attitude points with regards to the use of technology

	n	Min	Max	$\bar{X}$	Ss
Total Point	30	68.00	90.00	79.133	6.072

Examining the descriptive statistics calculated on the total attitude scores with regards to the use of technology as presented in Table 2, it was confirmed that the lowest point for the student was 68, while the highest point was 90. Considering that the highest point possible to be received from the scale is 95, it can be said that no students achieved to get this point. On the other hand, it can be seen that total point average of the group is quite high ($\bar{X}=79.133$; $Ss=6.072$). Considering that the lowest point for the scale is 19 and the highest point is 95, it can be said that the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education & training are quite higher than the average. Under these circumstances, it is observed that the teacher candidates display quite positive attitudes with regards to the use of technology in education and training.

The second problem of the research is as follows: “*Do the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme in education & training differ as gender-based?*” t-Test is set to be used for independent samples, as the parametric tests, in case of two sub-factors of independent variable, meaning the gender. However, the sample size must be at least 30 (Chakravarti, Laha and Roy, 1967). It can be seen that this requirement is met in terms of the size of sample. However, it is also required for the dependent and independent variables to display a normal distribution in order to use the respective parametric t-Test (Akbulut, 2010), within this context, the skewness and kurtosis values were analyzed for controlling the normal distribution. It is conferred that the skewness point for the attitude with regards to the use of technology ($skewness_{single\ attitude} = -.058$ and $kurtosis_{single\ attitude} = -.944$) is within the range of +1 to -1, and the kurtosis value is within the range of +2 to -2 (Blest 2003). Similarly, it can be seen that the skewness value as gender based is within the range of +1 to -1 ($skewness_{gender} = .000$). However, it was confirmed that the kurtosis value on this variable was out of the acceptable range of +2 to -2 ($kurtosis_{gender} = -2.148$). Therefore, the gender variable does not display a normal distribution. Additionally, Shapiro-Wilk test was set to be used, as one of the normality tests due to the size of sample ($n < 50$). Based on the results of this test, a normal distribution was conferred both for women ($D(15) = .956$, $p = .628$) and men ($D(15) = .911$, $p = .142$) (Shapira and Wilk, 1965). Besides, to Çokluk, Şekercioğlu and Büyüköztürk (2010) more than one situation is required to be set for

being used in identifying the distribution. Therefore, the histogram and interquartile graphics were analyzed, as well. Based on these analyses, both variables display normal distribution. It can be seen that the dependent variable “total attitude point with regards to the use of technology in education” and the independent variable “gender” display normal distribution”. The independent samples on whether the attitude points display a significant difference as gender-based, or not are presented in Table 3, following the t-Test results.

Table 3: t-Test results for attitude score with regards to the use of technology

	n	$\bar{x}$	Ss	t	Sd	p
Female	15	79.400	5.590	.237	28	.815
Male	15	78.866	6.706			

The difference observed as gender based within the attitude points of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education are not statistically significant ($t(28) = .237$, $p = .815$). Therefore, the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education and training do not display difference as gender-based.

The document, frequency and percentage analyses were used for the evaluation of answers given by the students to the following question, as the third problem in the research: “What are the challenges that are frequently confronted by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education and training?” The distribution of answers to this question can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: Frequency and percentage distributions for the challenges that are frequently confronted by the students while using technology in education and training

The challenges that are frequently confronted by senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education & training	Mentioning frequency / Total number of students	Percentage %
1. Confronting no challenge.	10/ 30	33.33
2. Tardiness of a technological tool used (smart board).	8/ 30	26.66
3. Not having the required knowledge for certain programs (i.e. smart board, etc.)	8/ 30	26.66
4. Internet connection cut-off (technical problems).	7/ 30	23.33
5. Failures of technological tool used.	3/ 30	10.00
6. Touch-screen problems of smart boards	2/ 30	6.66
7. Not using the up-to-date technologies	1/ 30	3.33

Examining Table 4, 10 of 30 students participating in the research stated that they confronted no challenges using technological tools & materials in lessons. 8 of the students mentioned that the challenge they most frequently confronted was the tardiness of the technological tool used. The technological tool implied for the tardiness is the smart board. 8 students participating in the research answered the question as not

knowing certain computer-based programs. Office programs, including certain features of the smart board were implied as an example for this challenge. 7 students answering the research question stated that they faced certain technical problems like internet connection cut-off during lessons. 3 of the students answered as the failures of technological tools & materials, while 2 of them mentioned the touch-screen problems of smart boards, and 1 of them mentioned the use of technological tools & materials that are not up-to-date in lessons.

The fourth problem of the research is “*What are the technological tools & materials that are frequently preferred with regards to the use of technology in education & training by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme?*”, and document, frequency and percentage analyses were utilized for the answers given to this question. The distribution of the obtained data can be seen on Table 5.

Table 5: The frequency and percentage distribution of technological tools and materials that are most frequently used by the students in the lessons

The technological tools and materials that are most frequently used by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme in lessons for education & training	Mentioning frequency / Total number of students	Percentage %
1. Computer	24/ 30	70.00
2. Smart board	17/ 30	56.66
3. Microsoft Office Programs	11/ 30	36.66
4. Internet	7/ 30	23.33
5. Smart Phone	5/ 30	16.66
6. Projector	4/ 30	13.33
7. Audio CD	3/ 30	10.00
8. Television	1/ 30	3.33
10. Video	1/ 30	3.33

Examining Table 5, 24 of 30 students participating in the research stated that the most frequently used technological tool was computers. 17 of the students stated that the smart boards in the classrooms were the most frequently used technological tool, while 11 of them answered as Microsoft Office Programs, 7 students answered as internet, 5 students answered as smart phones, 4 students answered as projector, 3 students answered as Audio CD and 1 student answered as television.

Under these circumstances, almost half of the senior students participating in the research do not confront any challenges with regards to the use of technological tools and materials. The leading challenges confronted by the students are the tardiness of technological tools used, internet connection cut-off, as well as not having the required knowledge for certain problems.

We can say that the technological tools and materials that are most frequently used by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme are the computers. Smart boards and Office programs can be categorized under the tools and materials that are most frequently preferred to be used by the students.

4. Conclusion

The objective of this research is to exert the attitudes of senior students in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology, as well as identifying the frequently used technological tools & materials, including the challenges confronted while using these tools & materials.

It can be clearly seen from the answers given to the question, as the first problem of the research *“What are the attitudes of senior students studying in the French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education & training?”* that the attitudes of senior students with regards to the use of technology in education and training is quite higher than the average. So it can be said that the teacher candidates display positive attitudes with regards to the technology use in education and training.

The second problem of the research is as follows: *“Do the attitudes of senior students studying in French Teaching Programme in education & training differ as gender-based?”*. Based on the answers given for this question, it was confirmed that there was no difference between the male and female students, considering the attitudes of senior students, studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education & training as gender-based.

The third problem of the research is as follows: *“What are the challenges that are frequently confronted by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme with regards to the use of technology in education and training?”* and following the analysis carried out on the answers that were given by the students, it was confirmed that almost half of the senior students participating in the research did not confront any challenges with regards to the use of technological tools and materials. The leading challenges that are most frequently confronted by the students are the tardiness of technological tools used, internet connection cut-off, as well as not having the required knowledge on certain programs.

Examining the answers given for the fourth problem of the research (*“What are the technological tools & materials that are frequently preferred with regards to the use of technology in education & training by the senior students studying in French Teaching Programme?”*), we can say that the leading technological tool & material that are most frequently used by the senior students is the computers. It was also conferred that the smart board and the Office programs are the technological tools and materials that are most frequently preferred to be used by the students.

In conclusion, it can be clearly said that the senior students (teacher candidates) studying in French Teaching Programmes are quite familiar with the technological tools & materials, and that they developed positive attitudes with regards to the use of these tools and materials. It is conferred that the leading tools and materials that are most frequently used in class environments are the computers, smart boards, and correspondingly the Office programs. So, it can be clearly said that the students will not confront any challenges while using these tools & materials on the point of their lives

when they are employed, and that they will not keep away from using these tools and materials in class environments.

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